

from 105 to 123 d and is shorter in tropical zones. Average yield is 8.5 t/ha, versus 6.4 and 7.7 t/ha for Timis and Diamant.

Topolea lines are lodging resistant, strongly resistant to cryptogamic diseases, and are N fertilizer responsive. *ℓ*

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Grain quality of hybrid indica rices in China

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About 8.8 million ha of irrigated land in China are planted to F₁ hybrids that yield 15-20% more than the best semidwarfs. Hybrids also produce high quality milled rice.

We evaluated 15 hybrid indica rice

and 2 semidwarfs for grain quality at CNIRRI in 1984. Grain was harvested, dried to about 12% moisture content, and analyzed by IRRI methods.

Length width of milled hybrid rice ranged from 2.3 to 3.2, averaging 2.7 (see table). Grains were medium-long or long. Chalkiness varied widely. All hybrids except Wei You 35 had fewer opaque areas than the semidwarfs. Shan You 32 and Shan You 36 were slightly chalky.

Amylose content (AC) varied from

17% to 30% in 14 nonwaxy hybrid rices. Four hybrids, including Shan You 2 and Zhong You 2, had intermediate AC. Shan You 85 and Jun You 85 had low AC. The hybrids had intermediate to low gelatinization temperature (alkali spreading value of 4-7 in 1.7% KOH), and softer gel consistency. Shan You 2 had the best elongation ability (180%).

Analysis showed that most indica hybrids had better appearance and cooking and eating quality than the two commonly planted semidwarfs. *ℓ*

Quality analysis of 15 indica hybrid rices in China, 1984. ^a

Variety	Parentage	Milled rice			Chalkiness (scale)	Amylose content (%)	Alkali spreading value (scale)	Gel consistency (mm)	Grain elongation (%)
		Length (mm)	Width (mm)	(Length: width)					
Shan You 2	Zhen Shan 97A/IR24	57	24	2.4	5	22	6.0	36.5	180
Shan You 6	Zhen Shan 97A/IR26	59	24	2.5	5	27	6.0	39.0	170
Shan You 32	Zhen Shan 97A/IR32-5	73	23	3.2	1	26	6.5	36.0	150
Shan You 36	Zhen Shan 97A/IR36	59	24	2.5	1	25	6.0	35.5	160
Shan You 50	Zhen Shan 97A/IR50	58	22	2.6	3	31	6.0	39.5	160
Shan You 85	Zhen Shan 97A/Tai 8-5	65	23	2.8	5	17	5.0	41.5	150
Wei You 6	V20A/IR26	66	25	2.6	3	28	5.5	42.5	150
Wei You 35	V20A/Zhai Zao 26	60	23	2.6	7	22	5.0	44.0	150
Wei You 64	V20A/Ce 64	67	23	2.9	5	27	5.5	50.0	150
Wei You 98	V20A/T 0498	65	22	3.0	5	26	7.0	46.5	140
Xie You 64	Xie Qing Zao A/Ce 64	67	21	3.2	3	26	5.5	52.5	140
Zhang You 2	ZMY Y A/IR24	69	26	2.8	3	23	6.5	46.5	150
Jun You 85	Jun Xie A/Tai 8-5	58	24	2.4	5	17	5.0	50.5	160
Qing You Zao	Qing Si Ai A/Houmeizao	57	25	2.3	3	20	6.0	33.0	170
Mei You 85	Mei Nou A/Tai 8-5	63	23	2.7	Waxy	—	4.0	122.5	170
Zhen Zhu Ai 11	Nonhybrid	56	23	2.4	7	27	5.0	32.0	150
Gui Chao 2	Nonhybrid	48	27	1.8	7	26	5.0	30.5	150

^a Av of 2 replications.

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